

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF RUDYARD KIPLING'S *THE JUNGLE BOOK* AND IT'S CINEMATIC ADAPTATION

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ABSTRACT

*Literature and Cinema are a powerful means of communication and they have an enormous influence on each one of us. Books and films have an enduring relationship amidst them. Most often cinema has turned to literature for inspiration, adapting it to a new language and image. Such adaptations have produced some of the finest moments in the cinematic tradition. Adaptations, more specifically film adaptations are significant in the sense that they offer a rebirth and reinterpretation to the once forgotten literary works through an audio-visual narrative. The phenomenon of adapting literature into film flourished in the late nineteenth century, and children's literature has left its own landmarks in the arena from Alice in Wonderland (1903) to recent Artemis Fowl, a 2020 American [science fiction adventure film](#) based on a young adult novel of the same name, written by Irish author Eoin Colfer in 2001. This research paper aims to explore the differences between the original book written by Rudyard Kipling, *The Jungle Book*, and its Cinematic Adaptation.*

Key Words: Rudyard Kipling, *The Jungle Book*, Cinematic Adaptation.

Rudyard Kipling is an Indian born writer of British origins, and one of the greatest storytellers of all times. Reading Kipling in India may seem as natural an activity as reading Kipling in England, or perhaps only a little less so, for he was an English writer with a crucial Indian dimension. Born in Bombay, he grew up picking the vernacular dialects of Indian speech. Kipling's initial years in India came to be seen by him as a lost paradise, which he later revisited in fantasy and by proxy through the child-hero of his greatest work, *Kim* (1901).

There are not many instances in the history of world literature of a major writer with such an intricately intertwined relationship between two countries. He belonged to one country by lineage and race but was born and bred in the other, was schooled in one but began his literary career in the other, initially won fame in the one for work written entirely in and about the other, and continued to write about the other even after he had left it for good. Indeed, it might be difficult to decide which country was Kipling's own and which, the other at least in the first half of his life. Kipling belonged to England but the works he wrote illustrate the deeply personal relationship that Kipling shared with the country of his birth, India.

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Rudyard Kipling is quite famous as a storyteller for children. I too read Kipling as a child, taking my first conscious delight in word-play from the Just So Stories and later relishing the rhetoric of the Jungle Books. Yet few children in the twenty-first century know more of Kipling than the Disney cartoon of Mowgli, Baloo and Bagheera, unless they happen to hear the Just So Stories read aloud by an adult enthusiast. Moreover, Kipling was a pioneer in anthropomorphic storytelling, especially in *The Jungle Books* and *Just So Stories*. He may not have been the first to combine anthropomorphism and song in children's literature, but he was the most prominent of the 19th century authors to do so.

Rudyard Kipling as a writer had the power of making the reader think on his lines. His stories depict knowledge about India and his experiences of having stayed here. He mentioned every detail in the *Jungle Books* right from the Oodeypore Palaces to the Himalayan Heights. He was engrossed by India. His travels around India had deepened his knowledge of her. He relished the strange scenes he had seen in his works. He had a profound knowledge of Indian life and character. He had studied Indian ways, languages, trades and customs.

Many nineteenth-century writers entered the visual age, one dominated by cinema and television; a number of them managed to survive; only a few positively thrived. Rudyard Kipling was in the latter group. The popularity of cinematic adaptations of his work has drawn fresh attention to his texts, reworking them within new cultural, historical and political contexts. While film adaptations of Kipling began to be made in the 1910s, he is best known for *The Jungle Book* which has inspired numerous other literary works and adaptations to television and film.

Rudyard Kipling's *The Jungle Book*, is the most popular work of his and has been adapted numerous times. There have been over 500 editions in 36 different languages. This all time classic book has been adapted into numerous films, the most famous being Disney's animated classic from 1967 and the most recent released in 2018. It has also been adapted into comic books for younger readers. Marvel Comics has been a pioneer in this field. Neil Gaiman's *The Graveyard Book* (2008) was inspired by the book, and Robert Heinlein's *Stranger in a Strange Land* (1961) concerned a child raised by Martians, not wolves.

The *Jungle Books* have always been a source of pleasure since time immemorial. Despite being 122 years old, *The Jungle Book* is one of those classics which is worth revisiting time and again. It is an iconic story, probably one of the most well known by young people and adults across several different generations. Since the publication of the book by **Rudyard Kipling** (which was rather a collection of books) in 1894-5, the story has become part of our collective imaginary for its universal, powerful messages, and for the unforgettable characters that populate it.

The interesting plot of a man-cub being raised by animals and the avoidance of didactic moral overtones made *The Jungle Book* popular among children. The primary characters, the language, content, length of stories, and readability levels are suitable for the readers in the age group 12-16. Eventually, the Mowgli stories' influence, which transcends any particular moral or allegorical structure, is felt most strongly in their language of description. Kipling's

close attention to physical details appears in the opening sentence of "Mowgli's Brothers", when Father Wolf 'spread out his paws one after the other to get rid of the sleepy feeling in their tips' (Kipling 1), and continues down to "Tiger ! Tiger!", 'Mowgli, with two wolves at his heels and a bundle on his head, trotting across at the steady wolf's trot that eats up the long miles like fire' (126).

The *Jungle Books* initially comprised of the Mowgli stories and some other stories until the 1897 version, for which Kipling himself opted to reorganise the stories in *The Jungle Book* and *The Second Jungle Book* so that the first contains all of the Mowgli stories in chronological order, while the second contains the rest. It may be stated that the Mowgli stories are the soul of the *Jungle Books*, and Kipling just tried to acknowledge their importance through this redistribution.

In fact, Kipling wrote the Mowgli stories backwards, which is to say that the character of Mowgli was first envisaged as a young man. The first Mowgli story was *In The Rukh*, a short story which appeared in the collection *Many Inventions* published, in 1893. It was from here that Kipling went back in time and imagined the wonderful life that the man-cub Mowgli must have lived as a child and the result was the Mowgli stories in *The Jungle Books*. Although originally published separately, *The Jungle Books* are usually combined into one volume. In *The Jungle Books*, the stories of Mowgli's jungle adventures are complete: The first book begins with baby Mowgli being nursed by wolves, and the second ends with Mowgli leaving the jungle. *In the Rukh* brings the Mowgli story full circle by showing Mowgli as a grown up man who marries the daughter of Abdul Gafur, and Mowgli's son playing with wolves.

Mowgli's adventures in fact take up only eight of the fifteen stories that make up *The Jungle Books*, but those eight stories captivate the reader's imagination in a way that the others do not. Mowgli's story is essentially a reworking of an ancient folklore theme, the child raised by animals. In most versions of this motif, human society remains the frame of reference; the child's animal existence is simply a prelude to his or her reintegration into humanity. In contrast, Kipling places Mowgli in the context of a complete jungle society, which appears more attractive than the few glimpses of the human world allowed into the stories. There are numerous themes coursing through the veins of this book, but Family and loyalty to family and friends, importance of rules and laws, courage and identity are the most dominant and recurring.

Kipling is keen on reinforcing the moral virtues considered important to late-19th-century Englishmen: bravery, loyalty, strength, rectitude, and a willingness to protect one's dependents. Most of the characters in *The Jungle Book* are brave and demonstrate their bravery through their willingness to defend, fight, or undertake an arduous quest. For instance, to save Mowgli from the monkey-log Baloo, Bagheera and Kaa used all their strength and tactics. Similarly, Mowgli shows consistent brave behaviour in his encounters with hostile wolf members, Shere Khan and Buldeo in the village.

From facing down Shere Khan's threats, to escaping the monkey tribe of Bander-Log, to being ostracized from a human village, Mowgli's conflicts primarily seem to sprout from the

main problem that he does not know where he fits in the world. He is clearly not an animal, but he does not feel like a human either. He is torn between his human heritage and the jungle world in which he has been adopted, and he struggles to find a place for himself that can reconcile these two parts of his life or nature. Kipling has very aptly portrayed this conflict in ‘Mowgli’s Song’, through these lines:

“Waters of the Waingunga, the Man Pack have cast me / out. I did them no harm, but they were afraid of / me. Why? // Wolf, ye have cast me out too. The jungle is / shut to me and the village gates are shut. Why?” (Kipling 133)

Relationships and events related in *The Jungle Book* are important to any human being, including adult men and women, with or without families. While the tales can be read, or children may listen to them from an older reader, these stories are enjoyable in every subsequent reading and the longer one lives, the broader is the frame of reference one has against which to draw the stories into perspective.

The *Jungle Book* is a story about respecting the environment and everything that lives in it, in addition to the adventures, friendships, courage and challenges, which children enjoy so much. The story explains how human beings are just one species among many that occupy the Earth, and how we should respect both the environment and the rest of the species that inhabit it. Every species fulfills its function in the circle of life. Every species is skilled at some thing and incapable of others. Through this story, Kipling tries to convey the moral value that encompasses the utopian significance of harmony between nature, wildlife and human beings.

The first adaptation of *The Jungle Books* was done by the Hungarian Korda brothers who brought to movie screens in 1942 Rudyard Kipling's *Jungle Book* in technicolor. This adaptation was a live action adventure and was told in the narrator's voice of Buldeo, the hunter of Kipling's book, to a visiting British memsahib. The narrative mostly focuses on Buldeo as he chases Mowgli through the forest. This adaptation took bits and parts from the first and the second *Jungle Books*, mixing Mowgli's miraculous childhood among wolves with the story about the treasure guarded by an old white Python which actually appeared in *The Second Jungle Book*, playing on all the available stereotypes of India as the land of wild beast and fabulous treasures, while keeping close to the original Kipling story.

The real breakthrough in the history of screen adaptations of the *Jungle Books* came with the Walt Disney Animation Studio's 1967 animated film version. Walt Disney himself supervised the making of the film and it happened to be his last. It was directed by Wolfgang Reitherman and the nineteenth film of the Disney camp. The film was a huge success and collected over seventy three million dollars in the United States in its first release and as much again from two re-releases. A live action remake of *The Jungle Book* starring Bruce Reitherman as Mowgli, was released in 1994. A theatrical sequel to its first *Jungle Book* movie as *The Jungle Book 2* was released by Disney in 2003. This sequel was not Kipling's *The Second Jungle Book*, but a continuation of the first Disney movie with a rather similar story line. The multiple remakes and adaptations point to the popularity as well as the unexplored potential for story telling inherent in *The Jungle Books*.

In India Mowgli became a household name after the telecast of the *Jungle Book* television series in 1993 on Doordarshan. The series, a compromise between the original Mowgli stories and the [Walt Disney version](#), received international acclaim and was aired in different countries around the world. It was especially popular in [India](#), where it was dubbed in [Hindi](#). The opening song, "Jungle Jungle Baat Chali Hai", composed by [Gulzar](#), instantly became a hit in India. The lyrics of this song were slightly changed for the 2016, live-action/CGI release of Disney's [The Jungle Book](#) in India.

In order to allow a more precise comparison with the original book that is itself relatively short, the selection limits itself to short films. Based on the box office success, good reviews, nominations, awards won and the popularity in India, I initially selected the following adapted films - *The Jungle Book (1967)*, *The Jungle Book (2016)* and *Mowgli : Legend of the Jungle (2018)* for a comparative study.

Finally, out of these three films, I decided on the animated film adaptation of 1967 because of two reasons (1). It's plot resembles the most with the original Kipling story and (2). It is made keeping in mind the interests of the child audience. The other two films are visual masterpieces but fail to adhere to the original narrative.

Disney's 1967 animated film differs from its literary source *The Jungle Book (1894)* in the following ways-

(a).It is mostly based on the first three stories, "[Mowgli's Brothers](#)", "[Kaa's Hunting](#)" and "Tiger-Tiger!" of the original book.

(b).Minor characters like Rann, the kite messenger and Ikki, the porcupine have been removed from the script.

(c).The meeting of the wolves at the pack council where Mowgli is accepted in the wolf pack on Baloo's recommendation and the bribe of a bull is cut from the film, which in turn, is described in detail in the original story by Kipling. In the film only the second meeting of the pack council is shown, in which Akela decides they can no longer protect Mowgli from Shere Khan and therefore he should leave the pack.

(d).Akela, the chief of the wolf pack, is just a prop in the film, quickly displaced by the arrival of Shere Khan. In the book Akela is threatened by members of his own pack who look to take his place as the clan chief. We see a little bit of this in the film, before Mowgli announces his decision to leave and as a result, we do not get to see Akela's character. He knows he is growing old and that he will be killed and replaced by one of his own kind. The bond between Mowgli and Akela is completely glossed over in the film.

(e).After bidding farewell to his wolf family, who ask him to return one day, he goes towards the nearest man-village. When he arrives, he is declared by the priest of the village to be the long-lost son of a woman named Messua, who was taken from them as an infant by a tiger. Messua finds out that he is not her missing son but a boy sent by the Gods to make up for the son being taken away. In Disney's version this part of the story has been deleted.

Apart from cutting some scenes and deleting some minor characters, Disney also added two minor characters, one of King Louie and the other of a young girl whose voice and look convince Mowgli to go to the Man-village. The [orangutan](#) species is not found in India and because the story is set in some Indian forest therefore, King Louie does not appear in [Rudyard Kipling's original book](#). This is further reaffirmed when Kipling states that the [Bandar-log](#) lack effective leadership, and so there arises no question of a king or ruler. The characterization of King Louie has frequently been cited as an example of racial stereotyping in Disney films but I think that a child watching *The Jungle Book* is unlikely to assume a racial dimension.

There are virtually no female characters in the story as well as the film that is read and viewed by both the genders. There are also only two female characters in the story, wolf mother Raksha and Messua in the man-village, both “having a maternal instinct.” In the film, Messua’s role is cut and Winifred’s added, who has no role but that of urging husband, Colonel Hathi to think about Mowgli in the context of their own little son. The other is the unnamed little girl who entices Mowgli to give up jungle life for the human village. Even though we can safely assume she’s only ten, like Mowgli, she’s portrayed as an adult siren.

The main events and characters, while simplified, are preserved but much of the dialogue is dropped to the extent that even the catch phrases such as “By the broken lock that freed me,” “By the bull that bought me,” “We be of one blood, ye and I,” “To each his own fear,” go missing, when they should have been lifted directly because these dialogues represent the important incidents from the life of the main characters.

Considering the themes as well as the ideological basis for the original work of literature is important in analyzing a film adaptation. The major themes running throughout the story are of abandonment and fostering, loyalty, friendship, importance of rules and laws, courage, conflict and interdependence of man and animal. Kipling does an exemplary job in portraying the inner conflict of Mowgli, arousing emotions through words -“These two things fight together in me as the snakes fight in the spring. The water comes out of my eyes; yet I laugh while it falls.” (Kipling 133). *The pathos of his condition, also powerfully* attractive to the adolescent, is that he does not know what is happening to him-“What is it? What is it?” ... “I do not wish to leave the jungle, and I do not know what this is. Am I dying, Bagheera?” (Kipling 41).

Disney’s adapted film also portrays the above themes though only superficially but completely loses out to the book by dropping the theme of Mowgli’s inner conflict. In the original Kipling story, Mowgli faces two types of conflict: internal conflict and external conflict. Internal conflict for the first time when he is driven out of the wolf pack and second time when he is turned out of the man-village. External conflicts are when Mowgli faces the Bandar-Log, Shere Khan and Buldeo.

The narrative elements obey the specific codes of a medium. In the case of a book, the interaction between both text and picture creates meaning and guides the reader’s feelings towards a world of fantasy. In an animated film - though the staging and the visual aspect itself play a very important role in the comprehension of the narration – emotions depend on

elements to do with time; the voices, the music and other sound effects, and especially movement. Kipling may not have been the first to combine anthropomorphism and song in children's literature, but he was the most prominent of the 19th century authors to do so. Kipling included songs in every story of *The Jungle Books*, as well as lyrical interludes between stories. The motive behind these songs and interludes could be the perception of a quality in the work which requires for its delivery the beat and lift of a rhythm which crosses and penetrates the rhythm of sense and logic. Narrative interludes cut through the silence between text to add rhythm to the story being told. This allows readers to connect concretely to the plot of the story.

Kipling proposed the jungle in his book to be full of music may be because it was written for the children and was much needed to balance the dark and sinister tone of the original story. Disney quite possibly liked this endeavor of Kipling so much so that he decided to make a musical animated film. The original songs in the 1967 film were written by the Sherman Brothers and Terry Gilkyson and are never at risk of being extraneous to the film. Their compositions had a key core strength: they locked the action, and the viewers, into the characters. "The Bare Necessities" is arguably the most alluring and theme song from the classic *The Jungle Book*. If we talk of the major changes, it's the climax and the resolution. The climax of the original story and the film where Mowgli encounters Shere Khan is entirely different in each version owing to the ideological difference of the writer and the director. The chapter "Tiger Tiger!" refers to the conflict Mowgli faces in having to kill Shere Khan. Shere Khan spends much of his time plotting to kill Mowgli, and Mowgli much of that time in preparing to face him. The song featuring in the beginning of this chapter poses initially naive but progressively perturbing questions to both Mowgli and Shere Khan- "What of the quarry ye went to kill? ...Where is the power that made your pride?"(Kipling 92).

Mowgli and Shere Khan both are facing pressure from within and around them to end each other. Shere Khan, protecting his reputation and own survival in the jungle and Mowgli being pushed to conquer his enemy like a man, are forced into deadly conflict against each other even though a more peaceful solution could have been reached keeping in mind that the story was meant for children.

The story ends with Mowgli regretting the brutality with which he killed Shere Khan. He realizes that destroying that which would have killed him without mercy destroyed a part of him. Killing nature, even for reasons necessary for us to live, hurts. The more we destroy, the more of ourselves we also compromise. The ambivalences marking Mowgli's drives, sympathies and identifications lead to a consequent compromise. This ending is not completely happy, does not find a complete resolution but rather hints at the beginning of another journey, full of more complex struggles that will make the character learn and grow even further.

Disney's resolution is a romantic one where an unnamed girl from the universalized man-village lures Mowgli to follow her to the man-village. He does not seem to do it as the consequence of a mature, conscious choice but rather because "he is hooked" by his own kind (the girl's innocent eyes and smile).

The original plot has less filters – life in the jungle is more dangerous – **and the characters show more complexity.** Therefore, Disney made changes that separated violence enough from reality to make it safe and enjoyable for a younger audience. And yet, the lessons are there and the fundamental value is not altered. It is a light-hearted feel-good story with happy songs and amusing characters. This film is about relationships, family, nature and living in harmony with it. These are important aspects children and humans in general have to deal with all their life. This film teaches how to behave towards others in certain situations, whom to trust and what true friendship means.

The book presents a story that not only entertains the children but leads them to think in a certain way, focusing upon an absolute good. Each child should relate to Mowgli and the characters of the jungle in different ways. Every child can take a different experience after reading it. Mowgli spends his childhood in the jungle, learning everything that the jungle can teach him about how to survive in the world. As a child, his teachers Baloo, Bagheera, and Akela all contribute to his maturation, problems that young readers can directly relate to, whether they concern friendship, family, respect, responsibility, or empathy with other living beings.

Thus we see that the most obvious differences between the novel and the adapted film are found in the scale, the level of realism they convey and the reflection of the author or filmmaker's ideology.

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